

CREAF

SEVERO
OCHOA
EXCELLENCE

SUMMARY OF CREAF'S STRATEGIC PLAN 2024-2028

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1. CONTEXT

The Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF) is a public research centre dedicated to terrestrial ecology, territorial analysis, and global change, pursuing excellence in the production and dissemination of knowledge, in addition to the innovation, development, and transfer of methodologies. The CREAM team (2023) includes 271 people working in research (78 permanent, of which 43 are PI, 36 postdoctoral researchers – including trainees –, 46 predoctoral researchers, and 84 research technicians), and 43 working in research management and administration (policy engagement, pre- and post-award offices, communication, research impact, academic talent and equity, fundraising, knowledge and technology transfer, infrastructures, modelling facilities, and TIC), including the general manager of the centre. The 50.05% of the whole CREAM team are women, who represent 41% of permanent researchers. (i.e., all researchers excluding postdocs and predocs), 27.9% of researcher PI's (i.e., leading projects) and 35.7% of staff joining CREAM's scientific boards and committees.

CREAF research is organised around four research areas and 8 excellence research groups (SGR) recognised by the Catalan Government. CREAM has experienced strong progress in research excellence during the period covered by the previous strategic plan (2014-2017, extended to 2023) and especially since the centre received its first Severo Ochoa award (end of 2019). Scientific production exhibits a steady increase across years up to 320 SCI articles in 2023. Furthermore, 91% of these articles have been published in journals in the first quartile (Q1) and 27.4% in the first decile (D1) in the last evaluation (2022). A recent benchmarking analysis showed that CREAM is the first among the centres analysed as for the number of publications and normalised

impact. CREAM also ranks first in terms of the percentage of international collaborations and in the percentage of these collaborations led by women. It also stands out in the number of publications per author, above the group average and the 75th percentile. These data confirm that CREAM is among the leading international centres in its field of research.

The recognition at Spanish level that came with receiving the Severo Ochoa award has gone hand in hand with growing international recognition, both of CREAM as a benchmark organisation in fields such as the impact of global warming, strategies to mitigate climate change and the conservation of biodiversity, and of its individual researchers. During the period 2017-2023, CREAM has intensified its participation in international networks, alliances, and expert working groups. CREAM has also shown remarkable success in H-Europe funding, with a three-fold increase in returns and a quadrupling of funded projects in recent years. Recently, CREAM has also strengthened its science-to-policy involvement through the participation in international and intergovernmental panels such as IPBES and IPCC and a new focus in science diplomacy.

CREAF has also deployed a highly skilled team of research managers during the last Severo Ochoa project that provides multiple support to CREAM direction and to research staff at any stage of their scientific career. Support of this team has helped to improve the collaborations among researchers, leading to an increase in co-authorship connections and network cohesion. CREAM's Ecosystem Modelling Facility (EMF), has enhanced CREAM's modelling capacity and collaborations among researchers. The team has also promoted the culture of impact in research and aligned CREAM's priorities with those of the EU,

by hiring one of the first Research Impact Officers in the Severo Ochoa programme. A Research Impact Strategy and its associated Impact Plans were developed to promote impact in all research proposals. The team also empowers researchers to improve their careers through specific Career Services.

The communication team has strengthened one of the best communication strategies in Spanish research centres, greatly increasing CREAM visibility. In the last years, CREAM has skyrocketed its communication to new heights, gaining 70% more social media followers, increasing visits to its news blog by an impressive 244%, and scoring over 300 media features despite intense competition. The centre has also engaged over 3,000 active volunteers in its citizen science projects and attracted 2,000 more newsletter subscribers, now totalling 6,500. CREAM's international communication has been developed by hiring a specific communication officer and developing an international communication plan to maintain communication with specialized thematic networks and develop an international newsletter. CREAM's communication team has also supported the development of several citizen science projects in various cities engaging over 3,000 active volunteers, and attracted 2,000 more newsletter subscribers, now totalling 6,500.

The CREAM team's research capabilities are strengthened by the availability of first-rate scientific infrastructures including 16 laboratories. CREAM's location on the campus of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona also provides CREAM with access to the UAB Scientific and Technical Services. Highly specialised analyses requiring high-throughput DNA sequencing techniques and high-class bioinformatics expertise are carried out in collaboration with external platforms, mostly within CERCA.

CREAM is also strongly committed to creating a diverse and inclusive organisational culture and has

developed a strong EDI (Equity, Diversity & Inclusion) strategy. The organisation has hired an EDI officer that leads the EDI Committee and collaborate with the Management Team to monitor and regularly evaluate the action plan implementation. CREAM made significant strides in improving the gender balance of researchers during the 2018-2022 period (before and after the development of the first Severo Ochoa award), especially those in leadership positions, with the proportion of women rising from 17.1% to 32.7% for senior researchers (i.e., all excluding postdocs) and from 19.4% to 27.9% for PI's. We have also increased the percentage of women researchers serving on scientific boards and advisory committees from 20.8% in 2018 to 35.7% in 2022. Thanks to a revision of our recruitment policy, 60% of researchers recruited, both junior and senior, from 2019 to 2022 were women.

Thanks to long-term policy and strategic planning, CREAM now boasts a quite robust financial situation, with a steady increase in the incomes and of the diversification of its sources and a global balance between incomes and expenditures. The basic pillars of current CREAM's financial situation include (i) the securing of the Severo Ochoa award, in December 2019, and its renewal in March 2024, (ii) the Grand Agreement (2021-2024) with the Government of Catalonia, in renewal by 2025; (iii) a thriving flow of EU funding, and (iv) increased funding from transfer activities, with an average of €1.4 million per year. Thus, the favourable financial position of CREAM can be attributed to a combination of a budget secured by the Trustees and a heightened ability to obtain external funding from a variety of competitive sources, predominantly public but with an increasing proportion of private funding. This has led to the establishment of a 75-25 model, whereby external sources have contributed around 75% of the total budget over the last five years, indicating that income from external sources is roughly three times the monetary contribution of the Trustees.

Considering the results obtained to date, the societal, political and economic context, and the SWOT analysis, the following 4 strategic priorities have been established for the period 2024-2028 (developed in 16 strategic goals, 40 operational goals and 66 actions):

1. To conduct and foster excellent scientific research relevant in a changing global context that enhances our leadership positioning at the national and international level. Focus will put on maximising CREAM's contribution to solving the current and future major environmental challenges and on promoting a culture of excellence and internal collaboration, while seeking the international projection of our research and improving technologies and infrastructures for its development.
2. To generate societal impact from CREAM's research, first introducing and fostering the impact perspective in our research strategy and practice, from planning to evaluation and including the development of consistent impact narratives. In this perspective, our science-to-policy work and our outreach activities shall require special attention. We will also analyse the market and social trends to find new opportunities for knowledge and technology transfer and we will develop a new KTT strategy.
3. To attract, retain and consolidate the talent that the centre needs to fulfil its mission. The priorities will be to fully develop the recruitment and talent management policies and systems, be able to attract the people the organisation will need to accomplish all their objectives, offer useful and comprehensive training programmes and career services, and foster the EDI (equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture within CREAM.
4. To ensure the centre's development and sustainability. We must, on one hand, reduce our CO2 emissions and implement procedures to be ecologically sustainable. On the other hand, we must explore our growing potential and take actions to guarantee the future increase of resources. Reviewing and improving our management model and creating the best work environment will be key assets for this purpose.

Image: Joan de la Malla

2. OBJECTIVES, AXES AND ACTIONS

The strategic priorities defined in the previous chapter have been developed in **16 strategic goals, 40 operational goals and 66 actions**, detailed in the following pages (actions included in the Severo Ochoa Strategic Plan are indicated with the code [SO AXX], being XX the action number in that plan).

In the area of **research**, efforts will focus on maximising CREAM's contribution to solving the major environmental challenges of the present and the future, and on promoting a culture of excellence and internal collaboration. To this end, we will be reviewing and updating when needed our scientific agenda in line with the priorities of international agendas and seeking synergies with other entities. All this, looking for the greatest possible international projection of our work and offering our team the most advanced technologies and infrastructures for the development of their research.

We also want to maximise the **societal impact** of our research, first by introducing and fostering the impact perspective in our research strategy and practice, from planning to evaluation, and including

the development of consistent impact narratives. In this perspective, our science-to-policy work and our outreach activities shall require special attention. We will also analyse the market and social trends to find new opportunities for knowledge and technology transfer and we will develop a new KTT strategy.

In the **talent** axe, the priorities will be to fully develop the recruitment and talent management policies and systems, be able to attract the people the organisation will need to accomplish all their objectives, offer useful and comprehensive training programmes and career services, and foster the JEDI (just, equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture within CREAM.

Finally, to be a **sustainable and efficient organisation**, we must, on one hand, reduce our CO2 emissions and implement policies and procedures to be ecologically sustainable. On the other hand, we must explore our growing potential and take actions to guarantee the future increase of resources. Reviewing and improving our management model and creating the best work environment will be key assets for this purpose.

Image: Joan de la Malla

RESEARCH

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.1 To foster trailblazing scientific research—both basic and applied—with potential to contribute to cutting-edge solutions to global environmental and social challenges	OG.1.1 To review CREAM research areas evaluating their potential to face current and future scientific and environmental challenges	A.1. Revised CREAM’s scientific agenda
	OG.1.2 To explore the alignment of major research lines to regional, national, and international agendas (e.g., SDGs, UN 2030)	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM’s scientific agenda
	OG.1.3. To explore agreements with the main academic trustees (UAB, UB, CSIC) to align our research agenda to their priorities.	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM’s scientific agenda
SG.2 To cultivate and enhance a nurturing research culture for excellence	OG.2.1 To encourage CREAM’s participation and leadership at targeted EU Projects	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]
	OG.2.2 To enhance internal collaborations among research groups	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Journal Clubs, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed ‘vermut’) [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]
	OG.2.3 To foster Open Science practices into CREAM’s research culture	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM’s Code of Conduct A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1] A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECOTONS) [SO A5.5]

SG.3 To position CREAM as a cutting-edge scientific institution internationally	OG.3.1 To promote the international exchange of researchers	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]
	OG.3.2 To increase CREAM's presence and participation in international research and environmental initiatives and platforms	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]
	OG.3.3 To consolidate our position as a referent scientific institution in the Mediterranean	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (MedCREAM) including science-to science, science-to-policy and science-to-business dimensions [SO A14.1]
	OG.3.4 To improve CREAM's international visibility	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.
		A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]
OG.3.5 To increase CREAM's visibility in the global community working on ecological modelling and forecasting under global change' and/or as a specific action.	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]	
SG.4 To provide our staff with state-of-the art facilities to carry out research of excellence	OG.4.1 To improve CREAM's facilities	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1]
		A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1]
	OG.4.2 To improve CREAM's digital infrastructure and technology	A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]
		A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]

SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.5 To work towards CREAM's own research impact culture	OG.5.1 To incorporate research impact within CREAM's institutional scientific strategy and practices	<p>A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1]</p> <p>A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for Societal Impact for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1]</p> <p>A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]</p>
	OG.5.2 To assess CREAM's research impact potential	<p>A.22. To structure an impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3]</p> <p>A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]</p>
SG.6 To maximise the societal impact of CREAM's research	OG.6.1 To improve and promote science-policy interfaces	A.24. To create a policy impact working group
	OG.6.2 To increase CREAM's opening to society and public support of science	<p>A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar) [SO A4.3]</p> <p>A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]</p>
	OG.6.3 To increase the social base of CREAM	A.27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan

SG.6 To maximise the societal impact of CREAM's research	OG.7.1 To develop the knowledge and technology transfer and innovation strategy	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's business opportunities A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1] A.30.To develop the IPR Management procedures
	OG.7.2 To consolidate the communication of KTT with the Generalitat	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan

TALENT

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.8 To improve talent management and development policies	OG.8.1 To develop CREAM career plan including the improvement of career advancement opportunities (promotion and salary)	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]
	OG.8.2 To fully implement the OTM-R policy	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R related actions at HRS4R plan
SG.9 To recruit researchers to ensure future sustainability	OG.9.1 To forecast personnel needs according to growth objectives	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative– replacement – and qualitative needs).
	OG.9.2 To gain international recognition as an attractive centre for developing a professional career	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan
	OG.9.3 To recruit and support researchers leading high quality research	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2. A12.3] A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]
	OG 9.4. To improve the PhD Programme	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts

SG.10 To develop career services for researchers	OG.10.1 To develop specific training programmes	<p>A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]</p> <p>A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]</p>
	OG.10.2 To develop the career development service	<p>A.43. To consolidate the CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]</p> <p>A.44. To consolidate the CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]</p>
SG.11 To create and foster an EDI (equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture	OG.11.1 To improve equality policies by introducing the EDI approach	<p>A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee</p> <p>A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI plan (2024-2027)</p>

SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTION

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG12. To ensure ecological sustainability	OG.12.1 Decrease CREAM CO2 emissions.	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]
SG.13 To assess the growing potential of CREAM	OG.13.1 To undertake a process of reflection on CREAM beyond 2025	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]
SG.14 To ensure economic sustainability	OG.14.1 To undertake a process of reflection on the sustainability of the centre with the Board of Trustees.	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)
	OG.14.2 To increase structural funds	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia
	OG.14.3 To diversify income sources	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]
		A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]
	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]	
	OG.14.4 To design a policy of prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide

<p>SG.15 To improve the management model and make it as efficient as possible</p>	<p>OG.15.1 To enhance management efficiency and transparency</p>	<p>A.55. To set up a CRIS, a general management Information System linking project research management to outputs and impacts</p> <p>A.56. To develop and implement the centre's Data Management Strategy</p> <p>A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy</p> <p>A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams' assessment performance</p>
	<p>OG. 15.2. To improve the strategy and management of research projects in all phases.</p>	<p>A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices</p> <p>A.60. To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management</p>
<p>SG.16 To improve CREAM's work environment</p>	<p>OG.16.1 To diagnose CREAM's work environment</p>	<p>A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM's environment and services</p> <p>A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey</p> <p>A.63. To do a conflict management protocol</p>
	<p>OG.16.2 To implant a hybrid working model</p>	<p>A.64. To define and implement a teleworking policy</p>
	<p>OG.16.3 To promote an international working culture</p>	<p>A.65. To promote English as a CREAM working language</p>
	<p>OG.16.4 To promote internal communication</p>	<p>A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.</p>

3. ACTIONS CALENDAR

*Those included in the Severo Ochoa strategic plan are indicated with the code [SO AXX], being XX the action number in that plan.

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
RESEARCH									
1	A.1. Revised CREAM's scientific agenda								
1	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda								
1	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda								
2	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]								
2	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed 'vermut's') [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]								
2	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM's Code of Conduct								
2	A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1]								
2	A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECO-TONS) [SO A55]								
3	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]								
3	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]								
3	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (MedCREAF) including science-for-science, science-for-policy and science-for-business dimensions [SO A14.1]								
3	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.								
3	A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]								
3	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]								
4	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1]								
4	A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1]								
4	A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]								
4	A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH									
5	A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1]								
5	A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1]								
5	A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]								
5	A.22. To structure an Impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3]								
5	A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]								
6	A.24. To create a policy impact working group								
6	A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar). [SO A4.3]								
6	A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]								
6	A.27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan								
7	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's bussiness opportunities								
7	A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1]								
7	A.30. To develop the IPR Management procedures								
7	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan								
TALENT									
8	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members								
8	A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]								
8	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R actions at HRS4R plan								
9	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative – replacement – and qualitative needs)								
9	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan								
9	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2. A12.3]								
9	A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]								
9	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology								
9	A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
10	A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]								
10	A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]								
10	A.43. To consolidate CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]								
10	A.44. To consolidate CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]								
11	A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee								
11	A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI Plan (2024-2027)								
SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTION									
12	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]								
13	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]								
14	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)								
14	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia								
14	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]								
14	A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]								
14	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]								
14	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide								
15	A.55. To set up a CRIS, management Information System linking project/research management to finance, outputs, and impacts								
15	A.56. To develop and implementation of the centre's Data Management Strategy								
15	A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy								
15	A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams' assessment performance								
15	A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices								
15	A.60. To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management								
16	A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM's environment and services								
16	A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
16	A.63. To do a conflict management protocol								
16	A.64. To define and implement a teleworking policy								
16	A.65. To promote English as CREAM working language								
16	A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.								

4. MONITORING AND EVALUATION: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI)

SG	KPI	RESPONSIBLE OF EXECUTION	REFERENCE VALUE	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2024-2028
1	KPI1. A revised scientific agenda of CREAM	Director-CRD	-			Y			Y
2	KPI2. Proportion of CREAM budget coming from EU (International) funding = (EU funding €) / (Total CREAM budget €)	Post-award officer	30	31	32	33	34	35	32.5
2	KPI3. CoARA action plan developed	CoARA working group	-	Y				Y (Reviewed)	
3	KPI4. MedCREAF strategy developed	Institutional relations officer	-	Y	(Published)				
3	KPI5. Science diplomacy and science 4 policy strategies and structures	Institutional relations officer	-		Y				
3	KPI6. A consolidated Ecosystems Modelling Facility (EMF)	Director-CRD	-				Y		
4	KPI7. Additional space of at least 1000 m2 achieved	Director-Manager				Y			
4	KPI8. Consolidated lab facilities of CREAM	Manager-CRD	-			Y			
4	KPI9. Consolidated digital infrastructure of CREAM	Manager-CRD	-		Y				
5	KPI10. Impact assessment and monitoring system structured	Research Impact Officer	-					Y	
6	KPI11. Impact service platform developed.	Research Impact Officer	-				Y		
6	KPI12. Social engagement (impressions in SSNN)	Communication officer	4.0M	4.0M	4.5M	5.0M	5.5M	5.5M	4.25M (mean)
6	KPI13. International engagement (% of foreigner followers)	Communication officer	30%	36%	40%	42%	45%	45%	40.7%
7	KPI14. KTT Strategy developed.	Transfer Officer	-	Y					
8	KPI15. New collective bargaining agreement implemented including a career promotion plan for all staff	Manager- Human resources officer	Y						

SG	KPI	RESPONSIBLE OF EXECUTION	REFERENCE VALUE	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2024-2028
9	KPI16. Annual number of R1 (predoctoral) researchers	PhD Program Coordinator – Academic Talent and EDI officer	41	42	43	44	45	46	44 (mean)
9	KPI17. Total number of successful ERC grants, MSCA-PF and Ramón y Cajal grants for R2, R3 and R4 researchers.	Academic Talent and EDI officer	ERC StG: 1 MSCA-PF: 5 RyC: 2						ERC StG/ CoG/AdG: 1 MSCA-PF: 5 RyC: 2
9	KPI18. Total number of new permanent seconded researchers (ICREA, UAB, UB, CSIC).	Academic Talent and EDI officer	6	2	2	2	3	3	12 (total)
10	KPI19. Number of courses with >10 participants in the Watering Talents training programme	Academic Talent and EDI officer	16	14	15	16	17	18	16
11	KPI20. Diversity of research staff during 2024-2028 = (percentage of recruited researchers that are women).	Academic Talent and EDI officer	43% (mean 2020-2023)						> 40% (mean)
11	KPI21. % of PI (or CREAM-PI) researchers in national or international projects that are women	Academic Talent and EDI officer	28	35	37	40	43	45	40
12	KPI22. Approval of the sustainability plan	Direction-Manager			Y				
13	KPI23. Reflection document finished	Direction-Manager			Y				
14	KPI24. Distance of structure funds to 33% of total (in % of total)	Manager	9 (2023)	8	7	6	5	3	6
14	KPI25. Amount of irregular funds (Philanthropy & TechTransfer)	Manager	25 000€	30 000€	50 000€	75 000€	90 000€	90 000€	67 000€
15	KPI26. Level of implementation of the process map (% of processes implemented)	Manager	0	25	50	67	85	100	65
15	KPI27. Data Management Strategy developed	Manager			Y				
16	KPI28. Employee Engagement/Satisfaction (Survey Scores, max 10):	Human resources officer	-	5		6		7	6

5. FINANCIAL PROSPECTS

Table of estimated costs of the planned actions, based on the Severo Ochoa Award funds, the contributions of the programme contract with the Catalan Government and internal resources.

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
1	A.1. Revised CREAM's scientific agenda	5000			5000
1	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda				0
1	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda				0
2	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]			60000	60000
2	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed 'vermut's') [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]			110000	110000
2	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM's Code of Conduct	5000			5000
2	A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1]			6000	6000
2	A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECOTONS) [SO A5.5]			40000	40000
3	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]			85000	85000
3	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]		10000	10000	20000
3	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (Med-CREAM) including science-for-science, science-for-policy and science-for-business dimensions [SO A14.1]			150000	150000
3	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.	5000			5000
3	A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]		10000	15000	25000
3	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]			368000	368000
4	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1]		1000000		1000000
4	A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1]			260000	280000
4	A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]			10000	10000
4	A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]			150000	150000
5	A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1]	5000			5000
5	A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1]			5000	5000
5	A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]			15000	15000

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
5	A.22. To structure an Impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3]			15000	15000
5	A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]	10000		5000	15000
6	A.24. To create a policy impact working group				0
6	A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar). [SO A4.3]	5000			5000
6	A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]				0
6	A.27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan	5000			5000
7	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's business opportunities	5000			5000
7	A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1]			140000	140000
7	A.30. To develop the IPR Management procedures	5000			5000
7	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan	5000			5000
8	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members	5000			5000
8	A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]			6000	6000
8	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R actions at HRS4R plan	5000			5000
9	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative – replacement – and qualitative needs)	5000			5000
9	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan	10000			10000
9	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2, A12.3]			820000	820000
9	A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]				0
9	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology	5000			5000
9	A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts		100000		100000
10	A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]			5000	5000
10	A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]			64000	64000
10	A.43. To consolidate CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]			45000	45000
10	A.44. To consolidate CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]			5000	5000
11	A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee				0
11	A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI Plan (2024-2027)	5000			5000
12	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]			9000	9000

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
13	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]	5000			5000
14	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)				0
14	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia				0
14	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]			40000	40000
14	A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]			63000	63000
14	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]			5000	5000
14	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide				0
15	A.55. To set up a CRIS, management Information System linking project/research management to finance, outputs, and impacts		30000		30000
15	A.56. To develop and implementation of the centre's Data Management Strategy	5000			5000
15	A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy	5000			5000
15	A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams' assessment performance	5000			5000
15	A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices				0
15	A.60. To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management		140000		140000
16	A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM's environment and services	5000			5000
16	A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey				0
16	A.63. To do a conflict management protocol	5000			5000
16	A.64. To define and implement a teleworking policy	50000			50000
16	A.65. To promote English as CREAM working language	5000			5000
16	A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.	5000			5000
		180000	1290000	2506000	3976000